

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

Deliverable n°:	D2.1
Deliverable name:	List of mineralogically suitable mine waste sites and sampling and treatment protocols
Version:	3.0
Release date:	13.12.2023
Type:	Report (R)
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Status:	Final
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Co-funded by
the European Union

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
V1.0	09.01.2023	Initial draft	Daniel de Oliveira
V1.1	20.01.2023	Document formatting	Filipe Neves
V2.0	31.01.2023	Adoption of the changes proposed by the reviewers	Daniel de Oliveira
V3.0	13/12/2023	Section 5.2.3, edition and improvement of Figure 24.	Daniel de Oliveira

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
WP2 / Task 2.1

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
Fm.	Formation
g	gram
IPB	Iberian Pyrite Belt
km	kilometre
kt	kilotonne
m	metre
Ma	mega-annum or millions of years
m.a.s.l.	meters above sea level
m.b.s.l.	metres below sea level
Mt	megatonne
NC	Neves-Corvo
ppm	parts per million
PQ	Phyllite-Quartzite Group
ROF	Rožňava ore field
t	tonne
TE	thermoelectric
VSC	Volcano-Sedimentary Complex
VMS	Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 2.1 of the START project is dedicated primarily to identifying potentially suitable old mine sites for supplying raw materials, in particular tetrahedrite-tennantite, to be used in p-type semiconductor thermoelements.

This task has been carried out by the five European Geological Survey institutions represented in the START partnership, from Austria, Germany, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain. Additionally, members of ASGMI's Mining Environmental Liabilities Expert Group (GEPAM), who have experience in old mine site sampling, characterisation, and evaluation of abandoned mining wastes, have been asked to contribute. In this aspect Colombia has also identified one potentially suitable mine site. Based on the volume of sulphides, the presence and content of tetrahedrite-tennantite and due to accessibility and logistical issues, these surveys have located suitable mine waste sites in the various countries, namely:

- Portugal – Neves Corvo (Sn-Cu-Zn) mine; Barrigão Cu-vein deposit; Brancanes Cu-vein deposit all in South Portugal within the Iberian Pyrite Belt.
- Slovakia – Strieborná Au-Ag-Cu-Sb vein-type deposit.
- Austria – Nöckelberg Stratiform Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag mine site, Schwaz stratiform Ag-Cu mine site both in Eastern Austria.
- Spain – La Sierrecilla; Rio Tinto mine sites located in Southwest Spain within the Iberian Pyrite Belt.
- Colombia – El Zancudo Ag-Au deposit, Titiríbi District, Northwest Colombia.
- Germany – Grube Clara (Cu-Ag vein type), Schwarzwald ore district, Southwest Germany; Bergwerkswohlfahrt (Pb-Zn-Ag vein type), Harz Mountains mining district, central Germany.

The identified mine sites will be considered donor sites containing mineralogically suitable sulphide minerals for producing the p-type semiconductor thermoelement.

The heterogeneous nature and distally located identified mine sites imply that the various teams carrying out the sampling need to have equal criteria for collecting samples. Therefore, a sampling protocol outlining methodologies is set out in this report. This takes the form of a scientifically sound approach to sample collecting and subsequent treatment of the samples will be created to maximise potential yields for use in the subsequent work packages.

4 MINE SITES CHOSEN FOR SAMPLING

4.1 INTRODUCTION AND DEFINITIONS

Substantial quantities of mining wastes, including rock, tailings and slag/metallurgical wastes are produced during the recovery of raw materials from primary mineral deposits (Hudson-Edwards et al., 2011; Lottermoser, 2011).

Wastes from mining operations can have several shapes depending on a series of factors largely related to the geology, ore deposit types and processing methods. Mining wastes are normally deposited close to the origin to reduce haulage costs, but it may be deposited further from the source due to practical reasons, due to limited stocking space or other infrastructural/mine planning reasons.

According to (Sädbom & Bäckström, 2018), there are four types of mine residues, namely:

- A. **Waste rock** – In a metal mining scenario, waste rock is bedrock that has been mined and transported out of the pit but does not have metal concentrations of economic interest. Waste rock includes granular, broken rock that ranges from fine sand to large boulders, depending on the nature of the formation and mining methods employed.
- B. **Waste rock dump** – A waste dump is an area where mining waste was deposited. It can have the shape of a pile or a fill in a previously depressed area in the terrain. Sometimes the mining waste is deposited in a depression and then naturally, the surface topography may not fulfil the definition to be called a pile.
- C. **Tailings** – Consist of ground rock and process effluents that are generated in a mine processing plant. Mechanical and chemical processes are used to extract the desired product from the mine ore run and produce a waste stream known as tailings. This process of product extraction is never 100% efficient, nor is it possible to reclaim all reusable and expended processing reagents and chemicals. The unrecoverable and uneconomic metals, minerals, chemicals, organics, and process water are discharged, normally as slurry, to a final storage area commonly known as a Tailings Management Facility or Tailings Storage Facility (Figure 1).
- D. **Stockpiles** – Crude ore (classified as ore in the mine or after sorting) is often stockpiled outside the mine area, the sorting building or close to loading docks, railways or roads for transport. Valuable material separated by various enrichment processes may be added to the same stockpiles or be stockpiled in separate piles. If the enrichment process includes product milling, then it is called a concentrate which is stored in a concentrate stockpile.

Figure 1: Aspects of some Portuguese mining wastes. Left – Tailings from Bugalho copper mine (Ossa Morena Zone); Right – Tailings from the S. Domingos VMS deposit and open pit with acid drainage (Iberian Pyrite Belt).

4.2 PORTUGAL

4.2.1 Neves-Corvo mine

Mine: Neves-Corvo (NC)

Country: Portugal

Type: Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS)

Status: Active mine

4.2.1.1 Historical Background of the Neves-Corvo mine

Neves-Corvo (NC) is a polymetallic base metal mine located approximately 220 km southeast of Lisbon, the capital of Portugal. More precisely, the mine is situated in the Alentejo province of southern Portugal, some 15 km southeast of the town of Castro Verde. Located in the Portuguese sector of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (Figure 2), one of the major VMS provinces of the world, the NC mine was discovered in 1977 by the Portuguese-French exploration consortium companies *Sociedade Mineira de Santiago*, *Sociedade Mineira e Metalúrgica Peñarroya Portuguesa* e SEREM/BRGM.

Figure 2: Simplified geological map of the Iberian Pyrite Belt, illustrating the location and name of the massive sulphide deposits and the principal Fe-Mn occurrences. VMS deposits: LS – Lagoa Salgada; RM – Rio de Moinhos; CAV – Caveira; LOS – Lousal; SES – Sesmarias; SL – Salgadinho; MO – Montinho; ALJ – Aljustrel; ALG – Algaré; NC – Neves-Corvo; CH – Chança; SD – São Domingos. Modified after Leca et al., 1983; Oliveira, 1990; Leistel et al., 1998; Oliveira et al., 2006.

Previous gravimetric works initiated by the *Serviço de Fomento Mineiro* (currently LNEG) in the Algaré sector enabled the identification of a large Bouguer anomaly located near the Neves village (Figure 3). This consortium completed the geophysical study of the region and through an extensive drilling campaign discovery the top of the Neves orebodies at about 350 m depth (Albuy et al., 1981; Barriga et al., 1997; Leca et al., 1983; Relvas et al., 2002).

Figure 3: Residual gravimetric anomaly map of Neves-Corvo region (Marques et al., 2020). Red colors represent the anomaly derived from high density rocks like massive sulphides and stockworks.

After the discovery, the *Sociedade Mineira de Neves Corvo* (SOMINCOR) started to exploit the deposit. Over the next years the SOMINCOR was owned by various companies that made a large investment in infrastructure development and drilling programs that allowed the discovery of large part of the deposits. In 2006 EuroZinc (previous owner) merged with Lundin Mining which currently owns the Neves-Corvo mine.

Neves Corvo is a world class deposit known for exceptional copper, zinc and tin contents. Originally counted with more than 300 000 tons of metallic tin with more than 60% Sn. The massive cassiterite found in NC is considered exotic worldwide.

4.2.1.2 Geological Setting of the Neves-Corvo mine

The NC mine (Figure 4) is located in the most important Volcano-Sedimentary Complex (VSC) structure in the Portuguese sector of the IPB. The mine site includes, so far, seven massive sulphide orebodies (Neves, Corvo, Graça, Lombador, Zambujal, Semblana and Monte Branco) ranging in depth between 230 and 1400 m (Lundin, 2017). The NC stratigraphic sequence is one of the most studied and best defined in the IPB, comprising from the base upwards of: **1)** Phyllite-Quartzite Group (PQ), a pre-orogenic detrital succession composed by dark shales with siltstones and quartzites intercalations (Givetian to late Famennian age, and base unknown (Pereira et al., 2008; Mendes et al., 2018, 2020). At the upper PQ sequence there are limestone rocks with crinoids (*Forno da Cal* limestones) usually associated with the first manifestations of volcanism (Oliveira et al., 2013); **2)** Lower VSC sequence, comprising bimodal volcanic rocks (felsic rocks and minor basalts), Corvo Fm. sediments (Famennian age), black shales of the Neves Fm. (Late Strunian age) and jaspers and carbonates at the top of these sequence (JC unit). Several rhyolite types have been classified based on geochemistry defining two volcanic horizons, at ca. 351 Ma and ca. 360 Ma (Solá et al., 2015; Albardeiro et al., 2017; Pereira et al., 2021). Massive sulphides are genetically associated with the latest and are hosted by the Neves Fm.; **3)** The Upper VSC sequence is represented by shales, siltstones and fine-grained volcanogenic rocks of the Ribeira de Cobres Fm., dark shales with siliceous-phosphatic nodules of the Graça Fm., grey shales with carbonate nodules, volcanogenic sediments and intrusive mafic rocks of the Grandãos Fm., Borra de Vinho Fm. purple and green shales, siliceous shales and volcanogenic sediments of the Godinho Fm, and above all the Brancanes Fm. black shales (Pereira et al., 2008; Oliveira et al., 2013); and **4)** The Mértola Fm., which is the lower unit of the Baixo Alentejo Flysch Group (BAFG) and includes intercalations of dark grey shales and greywackes.

Figure 4: Geological map of the Neves-Corvo region (adapted from Matos et al., 2020). In red, the surface projection the ore bodies (Neves, Corvo, Graça, Zambujal, Lombador, Semblana and Monte Branco) are shown.

Intense hydrothermal alteration is present (Morais et al., 2019; Morais et al., 2020). Concerning the metal distribution, one of the notorious characteristics of the NC deposit is the very defined vertical and lateral metallic zoning (Relvas, 2000). The highest contents of copper are generally located in the innermost areas of the stockwork ore type and at the footwall of the massive sulphides lens. The zinc and lead are covariant and concentrated to the most peripheral areas of the mineralizing system, laterally and vertically (Relvas, 2000; Carvalho, 2016). The tin occurs in association with areas of high content of copper, in form of cassiterite and sulfosalts, and its depositions are tectonically controlled, such as the tin corridor in the Corvo ore lens (Relvas, 2000). The principal characteristics of each type of ore and the general geology of each mineralized ore bodies have been extensively studied and described in previous works. The NC massive sulphides mineralization is composed mainly by pyrite associated with greater or lesser quantities of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, galena and cassiterite. Minor elements including arsenic, mercury, indium, selenium, antimony, gold, silver and others, occur within these minerals' internal structure or are associated with them.

Since the beginning of exploitation, the NC mine has been dedicated to the production of tin, copper and zinc concentrates, the last being exploited in major quantity in the recent years (ZEP – Zinc Expansion Project). The tin ore (exploited in the Corvo and Graça orebodies) is currently exhausted. The copper concentrates production has been growing since the beginning of activity with a production peak in 2011 with 3.198 kt of copper. The copper grade has been progressively decreasing (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Copper production data from Lundin Mining, 2017. *Left* - the copper production in the last years; *Right* - the copper grade evolution.

Data from 2017, indicate that the NC deposit has reserves (proved and probable) of 28.619 Mt with 2.6% Cu, 0.7% Zn, 0.2% Pb and 34 g/t Ag and 34.089 Mt with 7.5% Zn, 0.4% Cu, 1.8% Pb and 66 g/t Ag. It also has copper resources (measured and indicate) of 69.986 Mt with 2.7% Cu, 1% Zn, 0.3% Pb and 45 g/t Ag at a cut-off grade of 1% Cu and zinc resources of 106.819 Mt with 6.1% Zn, 0.3% Cu, 1.3% Pb and 58 g/t Ag (Table 1). The Semblana and Monte Branco orebodies are currently in evaluation.

Table 1: Neves Corvo mineral reserves and resources. Data from Lundin Mining 2017.

Total mineral reserves for Neves-Corvo					
Copper zones					
	Tonnage (kt)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Pb (%)	Ag (g/t)
Proven	6.423	3.7	0.9	0.2	35
Probable	22.193	2.3	0.7	0.2	34
Proven + Probable	28.619	2.6	0.7	0.2	34
Zinc zones					
	Tonnage (kt)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Pb (%)	Ag (g/t)
Proven	7.425	0.3	8.5	2.1	75
Probable	26.664	0.4	7.2	1.8	64
Proven + Probable	34.089	0.4	7.5	1.8	66

Total copper resources at a Cut-off grade of 1% Cu					
Resources classification	Tonnage (kt)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Pb (%)	Ag (g/t)
Mesured	14.732	4.2	0.9	0.3	44
Indicated	55.254	2.2	1.1	0.4	45
Mesured + Indicated	69.986	2.7	1.0	0.3	45
Inferred	12.758	1.7	1.7	0.4	37
Total zinc resources at a Cut-off grade of 3% Zn					
Resources classification	Tonnage (kt)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Pb (%)	Ag (g/t)
Mesured	15.464	0.3	7.7	1.7	67
Indicated	91.355	0.3	5.9	1.2	56
Mesured + Indicated	106.819	0.3	6.1	1.3	58
Inferred	11.386	0.3	4.4	1.0	52

4.2.2 *Barrigão mine*

Mine: Barrigão (BARRG)

Country: Portugal

Type: Veins structure (Cu)

Status: Closed mine

4.2.2.1 *Historical Background of the Barrigão mine*

The Barrigão copper deposit is situated within the SE part of the Portuguese IPB, one of the richest mining districts in the world, hosting some of the largest concentrations of massive sulphides, including several giant or world-class volcanic-hosted massive sulphide (VHMS) deposits, e.g., Aljustrel and Neves Corvo, with the latter being located only 10 km northwest of the Barrigão mine.

Copper ore extraction was carried out in the second half of the nineteenth century. The exploitation was underground in galleries and shafts with depths between 20 and 45 m, and the mining works were dispersed over an extension of 1800 m. From 1965 to 1973, the state-owned *Serviço de Formento Mineiro* (SFM) executed extensive pilot exploitation for copper reserves in the pre-existing mine galleries, which resulted in several dumps.

For the entire Barrigão deposit, which includes the *Cerro das Ferrarias*, *Cerro do Monte do Gato* and *Cerro de Martin Eanes* concessions, reserves of 36 000 ton of ore with 1.89% Cu are indicated (Araújo, 1977).

4.2.2.2 *Geological Setting of Barrigão*

The Barrigão deposit (Figure 6) consists of two converging metric thick vein structures, extending approximately 1800 m along strike (Matos and Rosa 2001; Matos *et al.* 2003). Several small secondary vein structures branch off the main structures. The veins cross-cut Visean shales and greywackes of the Mértola Formation, a subunit of the Baixo Alentejo Flysch Group (Oliveira *et al.* 2006). Exploration drilling carried out by SOMINCOR (Sociedade Mineira de Neves Corvo, SA) 2.5 km northeast of the old mine workings confirmed that the Mértola Formation continues at least down to a depth of 1140 m (Matos and Rosa 2001).

Figure 6: Geological map of the Barrigão deposit (Reiser et al., 2011). The anastomosing vein system, consisting of two major and several minor veins, cross-cuts a thick sequence of shales and greywackes of the Mértola Formation.

The Barrigão copper ore is represented by fault breccias composed of chalcopyrite, tennantite, tetrahedrite, and pyrite, with minor or rare arsenopyrite, löllingite, sphalerite, native bismuth, and an undetermined Cu–Sn–Ge-sulphide in a matrix of quartz, angular fragments of black shale, and carbonate minerals (Figure 7). The host rocks are siliceous greywackes and shales, consisting of quartz, feldspar, muscovite, plagioclase, chlorite, rutile, apatite, and graphite, with the latter sometimes locally enriched. Schistosity of the host rocks developed through strong foliation of mica and, where present, graphite (Reiser et al., 2011).

The ore samples revealed anomalous Sn and Ge contents with an average of 320 and 61 ppm, respectively, ranging between 16 and 872 ppm for Sn and 4 and 280 ppm for Ge. The outstanding values of Sn and Ge indicate their heterogeneous distribution in the ores, coevally implying their connection to distinct mineral phases. The wide range of values of whole-rock analysis data results

from the variety of samples collected: some Barrigão samples actually contain more gangue material than sulphide minerals, therefore exhibiting lower Cu, As, Ge, etc., contents.

Figure 7: Complex mineralogical association of chalcopyrite (yellow) and mixed sphalerite, tetrahedrite, tennantite minerals (grey) in Barrigão mine samples (Iberian Pyrite Belt). Photos Daniel de Oliveira.

4.2.3 Brancanes mine

Mine: Brancanes (BRANC)

Country: Portugal

Type: Veins structure (Cu)

Status: Closed mine

4.2.3.1 Historical Background and Geological Setting of the Brancanes mine

The Brancanes mine is located close to Neves-Corvo mine (approximately 3 km). Today shows ruins of mining infrastructures, which allow us to understand the methods and the scale of mining carried out there (Figure 8). The Brancanes Copper Mining Company initiated the activity in 1883, exploited a copper vein with N45°W, 50°E rich in chalcopyrite and pyrite with quartz and carbonates (Matos, 2007). The quartz + carbonate + sulphides veins are installed in shales and greywackes from Mértola Fm. In the superficial levels the copper mineralization was represented by malachite and rarely azurite and covellite.

Figure 8: Brancanes mine map with the location of the main shafts and galleries, 19th century (LNEG archive database).

4.3 SLOVAKIA

4.3.1 Strieborná mine

Mine: Strieborná

Country: Slovakia

Type: Veins structure (Au-Ag-Cu-Sb)

Status: Closed mine

4.3.1.1 Geological Setting of the Strieborná vein

The Strieborná vein deposit of the Rožňava ore field (ROF) is situated at the south-eastern margin of the Western Carpathian basement units, inside the Gelnica Group formation of the Gemeric Superunit. The Early Paleozoic Gelnica Group forms the oldest sequence of the metasedimentary/metavolcanitic formations of the Gemeric Superunit. The ROF area is penetrated by the subparallel arranged hydrothermal siderite– sulphidic veins of SE–NW direction. The history of mining in the ROF started in the 13th century, when the greatest interest was focused mainly on gold (Eisele, 1907), silver, copper (Schifter, 1938; Pavlík, 1967), antimony (Papp, 1915) and mercury (Herčko, 1971). In 1981, northwards from the Rožňava mining city, a new Strieborná vein was discovered near the Čučma village, and it became the most significant vein structure in the ROF. The vein position was compared with the historically known, parallel oriented Mária vein (Mesarčík, 1994). The veins are situated in the NE–SW transpressive Transgemeric shear zone (Maťo & Sasvári, 1997) where the Strieborná vein is divided into boudine structure, while the Mária vein is relatively solid. The distance between the Strieborná and Mária veins is 600 m (Figure 9). The vein filling and the structural position in the ore field suggest a close link between the veins

origin and structural evolution. The Strieborná vein genesis is the product of multiple epigenetic hydrothermal mineralization (Sasvári & Maťo, 1998; Hurai et al., 2002), with a close relationship between the vein filling and rheologically contrasting environment. Consequently, the vein does not crop out on the surface. The largest accumulation is known from the 10th mine horizon (20 m.b.s.l.) in the total length of 1300 m. On this horizon, the veins have an NNE–SSW direction and general inclination 75–85° to the NNW, where the vein abruptly ends. The continuation of the vein gradually decays in the overlying darkblack metapelites and grey metasandstones. Metaclasts often contain layers of quartz and lithic wackes. Below the 10th level (below 0 m.a.s.l.) the ore body is situated within metasediments and metavolcanic rocks.

Figure 9: Geological cross-section through the NE part of Rožňava–Mária ore segment (Mesarčík et al., 1991— modified). 1 — recrystallized metavolcanics (mafic pyroclastics); 2 — metasandstones interbedded by keratophyre metapyroclastics; 3 — altered grey metasandstones with black phyllite intercalations; 4 — coarse laminated metasandstones intercalated by green-grey phyllites; 5 — ore veins; 6 — mining levels; 7 — prospecting hole; 8 — faults; 9 — sampling location. The age of volcano-sedimentary complex is Late Paleozoic. The inset shows the location of the Rožňava ore field (ROF).

4.3.1.2 Mineralogy of the Strieborná vein

Major vein minerals are medium to the coarse-grained siderite of two generations and younger multi-generational quartz–sulphide mineralization of two generations. The most abundant ore minerals are tetrahedrite, chalcopyrite, pyrite and arsenopyrite. Brittle, steel-grey coloured tetrahedrite, which is the most important ore mineral, is spatially controlled by the older siderite that is in the form of reticulated veins and clusters. A more brittle tetrahedrite variety with steel blue colour and high metallic lustre is usually enriched by Cu, Ag, Bi, Sb and Hg. A darker low lustre variety contains more Zn and Fe (Sasvári & Maťo, 1998). The high content of silver in tetrahedrite was the reason for the name of the Strieborná vein. The concentration of tetrahedrite in the vein

bodies has a zonal distribution, and gradually decreases downwards to underlying rocks where it is substituted by pyrite (Mesarčík et al., 1991; Maťo & Sasvári, 1997; Sasvári & Maťo, 1998). Quartz is the main gangue mineral and forms several generations (Sasvári & Maťo, 1998). The products of the youngest quartz– sulphide phase are tetrahedrite, kobellite, bismuthinite, bournonite, jamesonite and stibnite.

4.4 AUSTRIA

4.4.1 Nöckelberg mine

Mine: Nöckelberg

Country: Austria

Type: Stratiform (Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag)

Status: Closed mine

The site was chosen for its rich content of tennantite in the mine waste, as well as for accessibility and logistical reasons (approval of property owner).

4.4.1.1 Location and geological setting of the Nöckelberg mine

The mine waste site Nöckelberg is located near Leogang in the province of Salzburg on the northern flank of the Schwarzleobach valley (Figure 10). Here, Devonian dolomites and phyllites of the Greywacke zone are thrust upon sandstones and conglomerates of the Calcareous Alps. The site is located in a forest at 1300 m altitude. The waste heaps consist of pebble- to boulder-sized rock fragments (Figure 11). Samples were taken from the waste heap in front of the Ottental adit.

Figure 10: Location and geology of the Nöckelberg area (Braunstingl et al., 2009).

Figure 11: Mine waste heap at Nöckelberg.

4.4.1.2 Mining and mineralogical data of the Nöckelberg mine

The historic mine site is part of the Leogang ore district, featuring a polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag sulphide mineralization (Weber et al., 1997). The ore is hosted by silica bearing dolomites (Spielbergdolomit) and associated with early alpine NE-SW trending tectonic structures (Lengauer & Paar, 1989). The stratiform deposit is the result of syn-sedimentary, hydrothermal mineralization due to submarine, basic volcanism during the Palaeozoic (Heinisch, 1987). Mining operations at Nöckelberg took place in the 19th and early 20th century. The remaining, large heaps of mine waste have an estimated volume of 45,000 m³ (Feitzinger et al., 1998). Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopyrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite. Table 2 lists the results of chemical analyses of fahlore at Nöckelberg (Schroll & Azer, 1959). Fahlore content in the mine waste remains to be quantified.

Table 2: Element contents of fahlore at Nöckelberg (Schroll & Azer, 1959).

As (%)	Sb (%)	Ag (%)	Zn (%)	Fe (%)	Pb (%)	Ge (ppm)	Sn (ppm)	Ni (ppm)	Co (ppm)	Mn (ppm)
20	0,5	<0,001	0,03	0,1		70		20	45	
20	0,9	<0,001	0,04	3		80	150	45	50	300
10	>10	<0,001	0,3	0,3	0,008		20	35	75	

4.4.2 Schwaz mine

Mine: Schwaz

Country: Austria

Type: Stratiform (Ag-Cu)

Status: Closed mine

The site was chosen for the high content of tetrahedrite in the mine waste, as well as for the simplicity of separating ore from waste rock.

4.4.2.1 Location and geological setting of the Schwaz mine

Several mine waste sites are located on the southern flank of the Inn valley near Schwaz (province of Tyrol) (Figure 12). Here, Ordovician and Silurian schists of the Greywacke zone are thrust upon carbonate rocks of the Calcareous Alps (Pirkl, 1961).

Figure 12: Location and geology of the Schwaz area (Brandner et al., 1980)

The extensive mining area stretches over 6 km and includes dozens of mine waste sites ranging in altitude from 540 to 1200 m above sea level. Three of these sites were sampled, two scree slopes (“Antoni” and Sigmund” mine waste sites) which consist of pebble- to boulder-sized rock fragments, and one sand deposit (“Sandpocher”) which represents the processing remains of crushing followed by gravity separation with water (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Mine waste heaps “Sandpocher” and “Sigmund” at Schwaz.

4.4.2.2 Mining and mineralogical data of the Schwaz mine

The historic mine sites are located within the fahlore district of Schwaz - Brixlegg (Weber et al., 1997), the sampled sites being part of the Falkenstein area. Silver and copper have been mined here since the Bronze Age. In the 15th and 16th centuries, Schwaz represented one of the biggest European mining towns, producing 19 % of Europe’s silver (Gstrein, 2013). Ore mining ended in 1957.

Mineralized fractures as well as stratiform ore bodies of 3 m thickness occur in dolomite host rocks, the dominant ore mineral is Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite (Frimmel, 1989). The mineralization is due to hydrothermal fluids leading to layered metal deposits which were later remobilized. Table 3 lists the results of chemical analyses of fahlore at Schwaz (Schroll & Azer, 1959). Fahlore content in the mine waste remains to be quantified.

The estimated volume of the “Sandpocher” site was estimated at 12,000 m³ (Benold, 2020), the “Antoni” and Sigmund” waste heaps cover an area of 12,000 m² and 49,000 m², respectively.

Table 3: Element contents of fahlore at Schwaz (Schroll & Azer, 1959).

As (%)	Sb (%)	Bi (%)	Ag (%)	Zn (%)	Hg (%)	Fe (%)	Pb (%)	Cd (ppm)	Ge (ppm)	Sn (ppm)	Ni (ppm)	Co (ppm)	Mn (ppm)
5,4	20	0,04	0,2	>10	4	5,2	0,03	200	45		300	100	60
3	>20	0,8	2,8	>10	4	5,5	0,03	370			150	150	200
7,2	>10	0,05	0,1	7,2	1,5	>10	0,015	130	15		150	400	70
6,4	16,56	0,03	0,1	5,77	0,83	1,53	0,008	100	40	10	70	300	20
2,6	>20	0,5	0,3	10	0,21	4,3	0,003	10	50	20	70	35	
8	>10	0,04	0,04	7,4	2,2	1,2		85			75	35	
5,4	20	0,7	2,5	>10	5,4	6,2		65	170				650
10	>10	0,3	0,4	2	1,4	5,5	0,006	75			600	150	35
≥10	>10	0,3	0,3	10	3,2	4,2	0,002	40	15		1400	400	
9,3	>10	1	1	1,5		4,4	0,002	20			750	600	

4.5 SPAIN

4.5.1 La Sierrecilla mine

Mine: La Sierrecilla (LS)

Country: Spain

Type: Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS)

Status: Closed mine

This mine site, located in the Spanish sector of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) (Figure 14), has been chosen because of its relatively high content of tetrahedrite compared with the rest of mines set in the same area. The old mining works, currently included in a wide mining exploration permit, belong to the “*Emerita Resources España*” company. The mentioned company has given permission to carry out the sampling.

Figure 14: Location and geology of the Sierrecilla mine (modified García de Miguel, et al., 1986).

4.5.1.1 *Historical background of the Sierrecilla mine*

The deposit was mined in the past, at the end of the 19th century, by means of underground mining. The workings reached a depth of 60 m. Two mine shafts were sunk at either end of the orebody, east and west. It is estimated that the mine waste contains about 5,000 m² of relatively abundant mineralization: sphalerite-galena and tetrahedrite. These were discarded due to metallurgical problems.

Between 1970-1980, the ore deposit was investigated by Asturiana de Minas, Phelps Dodge and Riotinto Minera companies. The reserves were 1 Mt with 1.54% Cu, 5% Pb, 12% Zn and 500 gr/t (Leistel et al., 1998).

4.5.1.2 *Location and geological setting of the Sierrecilla mine*

The old “La Sierrecilla” mine is located in the municipality of Puebla de Guzmán (Huelva), in western Andalucía, very close to the border with Portugal. The mine is 7,5 kms east of the very large “Romanera” deposit.

The “La Sierrecilla ” copper deposit is located in the NW Spanish IPB. This is one of the richest districts in the world, with some of the largest concentrations of massive sulphides, including several large or volcanic-hosted massive sulphide (VHMS) deposits.

Geologically, the ore deposit is located in the Northern Domain (Quesada, 1996), where the Volcano-Sedimentary sequence consists mainly of massive, submarine, acidic, intermediate and basic lavas interbedded with fine-grained sediments, concretely the Paymogo Volcano-Sedimentary Alignment.

The stratiform mineralization is 800 m long and metric thickness, with N119 E, 75 N. A fault with N35E cuts the orebody (Figure 15).

The most abundant ore minerals are pyrite, sphalerite, galena, tetrahedrite and chalcopyrite. As minor minerals are bornite, barite and colusite, and as supergenic ones, bornite, covellite and chalcocite.

García de Miguel (1986), after studying studied 68 polished sections taken from cores, determined that the most abundant metallic ores in the La Sierrecilla deposit were sphalerite-galena following by tetrahedrite.

Tetrahedrite from this deposit is a greenish grey variety that is found in the sphalerite matrix; nevertheless, in some areas, tetrahedrite are the dominant ore mineral. In these cases, it forms a continuous phase with other sulphides. Occasionally, tetrahedrite occurs as bands, along with pyrite and sphalerite/galena.

Regarding the ore textures, three types of ore minerals can be distinguished:

- Ore minerals rich in sphalerite – galena. In these ores, the most abundant mineral is sphalerite, followed by galena. The tetrahedrite appears as irregular grains and zones within the sphalerite. In galena-rich areas, tetrahedrite occurs as individual grains within galena.
- Ore minerals rich in chalcopyrite. It usually appears in deeper areas of the mineralized mass.

- Ore minerals rich in pyrite

The mineralization is highly recrystallized and shows ductile deformation effects, which testifies to the intense deformation it has undergone.

Figure 15: Geological sections of the La Sierrecilla Mine (García de Miguel, et al., 1986).

4.5.1.3 Spatial distribution of the different ore minerals in the Sierrecilla mine

The different types of ore minerals are distributed homogeneously throughout the deposit. Sulphides occur massively in the core of the mineralized zones, and the gangue are concentrated in the most peripheral areas.

The tailings dumps are spread out over a relatively small area (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Satellite view of the tailings of the Sierrecilla mine.

4.5.2 Rio Tinto mine

Mine: Rio Tinto (RT)

Country: Spain

Type: Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS)

Status: Active mine

The site was chosen, first of all, for the large volume of sulphides contained in the mine waste, although the percentage of tetrahedrite is relatively low. Secondly, because of the facilities offered by the mining company that sources the deposit (Atalaya Mining).

4.5.2.1 Location and geological setting of the Rio Tinto mine

Rio Tinto is located 80 km NW of Seville (Figure 17). The mine is currently active, so accessibility to the tailings is good.

Geologically, it belongs to the South Portuguese Zone, the southernmost of the zones in which the Iberian Massif is divided. The Iberian Pyrite Belt is one of the most important volcanogenic massive sulphide districts in the world and has been mined during more than 5000 years by the Tartessians, Phoenicians, Romans, Arabs, British and Spanish.

Figure 17: Geological sketch with expression of materials, tectonics and mineralisation.

From the geological point of view, Rio Tinto district is located on a thrust sequence dipping to the south and folded and overthrust by the Culm Group, creating a syncline structure (Rio Tinto syncline) with an E-W direction. The local stratigraphy consists of:

- Slates and Quartzites of the PQ Group.
- Slates with interbedded basalt flows and volcanoclastic mafic rocks, intruded by rocks with the same composition (Siliciclastic Mafic Unit).
- Acid Unit, consisting of massive felsic rocks (dacites/rhyodacites), hyaloclastites and volcanoclastic rocks, at times rich in pumice, glass and crystals. They are also interbedded with slate.
- Dark slate with conglomerates, dominant in the lower part of the sequence. In the upper part there are purple and green slates, and the massive sulphides are beneath them, covered by a white chert level.

This horizon has been dated as Early Tournaisian and therefore is more recent than the one over the massive sulphides of the Southern Zone of the Pyrite Belt, which is barren in the Rio Tinto area.

This apparently simple stratigraphy is complicated by the presence of abundant faults and thrusts, together with an overall hydrothermal alteration frequently masking the original structural relationships.

4.5.2.2 Mining and mineralogical data of the Rio Tinto mine

The mineralization is found either as dissemination or small veins in the stockwork areas within volcanic rocks and slates, or as massive sulphide lenses lying atop or included in the stockwork zones, or in gossan areas representing the supergenic alteration of massive sulphides, sometimes up to 70 m thick.

The massive sulphides form three bands where discontinuous and subvertical lenses are lined up (Figure 18):

- Deposits located in the southern side of the structure, as well as in the so-called Southern Lode which includes the Southern Vein itself, San Dionisio and Atalaya.
- Deposits located north of Cerro Colorado, including the Northern Vein, Salomón, Lago and Quebrantahuesos, which are in the northern side of the structure.
- Deposits located further east (Planes-San Antonio) There does not seem to be a continuity between the mineralization of the Northern and Southern Lodes.

Actually, what makes Rio Tinto different from other districts in the Pyrite Belt is the fact that the massive sulphides seem to be formed in two different environments. On one side, the mineralization in Southern Lode and Planes-San Antonio are hosted in slates and have sedimentary structures, suggesting they were formed by exhalative processes in the sea bottom. However, the mineralization in the Northern Vein hosted by dacite have a coarser grain and always display replacement structures with the hosting dacite.

Figure 18: 3D diagram of the Rio Tinto deposit (<https://riotinto.atalayamining.com/una-actividad-con-un-importante-potencial-minero/>).

The stockwork of Cerro Colorado is very big, over a surface of around 3 km². Generally, there seems to be a strong lithological control on the type of alteration (Figure 19). Mafic volcanic rocks and slates are only affected by chloritic alteration, whereas felsic volcanic rocks are mainly affected by a sericitic alteration, appearing the chloritic alteration just in the zones of the maximum alteration, commonly near faults. Overall, it seems that the chloritic alteration zones are enriched in copper,

whereas those of sericitic alteration are enriched in zinc. The original structure of the area has been severely modified by Variscan faults and thrusts.

Figure 19: Rio Tinto Mine overview.

The mineralization was supergenically altered and eroded during the Cenozoic. Originally, there was a gossan (Cerro Colorado) of 10-70 m depth (average, 30 m) mined between 1974 and 2002 together with the copper of the underlying stockwork (1973-1986).

The gossan was rich in Au, Ag, Pb, Sb and Bi, and poor in Cu and Zn. Grades were approximately 79% Fe₂O₃, 1.2% Pb, small amounts of Cu and Zn, 1.8-2.5 g/t Au, and 35-45 g/t Ag. There is a transported gossan (Alto de la Mesa) around 10 m thick with insignificant metal content. It is interpreted as a result of chemical weathering in a river basin controlled by a fracture.

Mineralization is typical of the VMS deposits and occurs as three different types: sulphide stockworks in the volcanic rocks; massive sulphide orebodies, generally, on top of the stockwork zones and/or intercalated with rocks of the transition series; and weathering products of the mentioned primary mineralization types, which are represented by gossans and secondary enrichment zones. The latter are restricted to within 70 m of the surface.

The stockworks occur as irregular veins, fractures, and fissures filled with quartz and sulphides (pyrite, chalcopyrite, galena, sphalerite), magnetite, quartz, chlorite, calcite, and barite cutting the volcanic host rocks.

Massive sulphide mineralization consists of lenses of massive pyrite overlaying the felsic volcanic and the stockworks, usually with greater lateral extent than the stockwork zones. The primary sulphide mineralization consists mostly of pyrite, with minor chalcopyrite, sphalerite, galena, tetrahedrite, and sulfosalts of Sb and As in intergranular spaces or in microfractures. Chalcopyrite

is the dominant copper mineral and mostly occurs within small fractures in the pyrite; on a lesser extent it occurs in isolation.

Gossans and secondary mineralization have formed in places over the stockwork and sulphide mineralization. Leaching and oxidation of an important volume of sulphides in Cerro Colorado and minor amounts in the Atalaya pit developed extensive gossans, which were mined for gold and silver. Gossans and supergene enrichment zones are characterized by the occurrence of secondary minerals, goethite-limonite and chalcocite-covellite respectively.

4.5.2.3 Reserves and Resources of the Rio Tinto mine

Recently updated Statement estimates Proven and Probable Ore Reserves total 197 million tonnes at 0.42% copper (0.82 million tonnes of contained copper). Measured and Indicated Mineral Resources total 258 million tonnes at 0.40% copper (Table 4).

Table 4: Estimates of proven and probable ore reserves in Rio Tinto.

Reserves	Mt	Cu%
Proven	128	0.41
Probable	69	0.44
Total Ore Reserves	197	0.42
Resources	Mt	Cu%
Measured	152	0.39
Indicated	106	0.40
Total Measured & Indicated Resources	258	0.40

4.6 COLOMBIA

4.6.1 El Zancudo mine

Mine: El Zancudo

Country: Colombia

Type: Ag-rich vein-type Ag-Au ore deposit

Status: Close mine with current exploration project

4.6.1.1 General aspects of the El Zancudo mine

The El Zancudo mine is part of the so-called Titiribí Mineral District in proximity of the populated nucleus of the Titiribí municipality, located on the western flank of the Colombian Central Cordillera (Figure 20). In this gold-silver district, mining activity dates back to pre-Columbian times, however, continuous production began in colonial times since 1793, with greater production in the period between 1880 and 1910, with the operation of at least 14 mines, which were closed in 1945. During the period between 2000 and 2010, only one El Zancudo mine, along the La Independencia tunnel,

advanced exploitation work and several exploration projects were activated (Leal- Mejía, 2011, and references cited there).

Figure 20: Location of the El Zancudo mine.

4.6.1.2 Geological environment of the El Zancudo mine

The District of Titiribí is in a suture zone, so the basement here is a "tectonic melange" made up of wedges of Paleozoic quartz-sericitic schists (para-autochthonous) and Cretaceous volcanic and sedimentary rocks with oceanic affinity (allochthonous) (Figure 21). On this basement lie native sequences of siliciclastic sedimentary rocks of Oligocene age, deposited in a marine-continental transitional environment. The terrains made up of these rocks underwent deformation because of a compressional regime, generating a structural style where reverse faults verging to the E are notorious. Both the melange rocks and the sedimentary rocks that cover them were syntectonically intruded by plutons, dykes and silos of dioritic to monzonitic composition, ca. 6-9 Ma. (Redwood, 2010; Leal-Mejía, 2011, and references therein).

Figure 21: General geological map of the El Zancudo mine. (source: <https://www.mindat.org/loc-206716.html>).

4.6.1.3 Characteristics of the deposit of the El Zancudo mine

Mineralization occurs around and within porphyritic intrusive bodies. Two main types of mineralization have been described in the Titiribí District:

- 1) High-grade Au-Ag (Zn-Pb-Cu-As-Sb) deposits, which consist of stratigraphically controlled veins and mantles like those found in the El Zancudo mine. The most important mineralizations of this type are vein systems with variable thickness and that have been mined for hundreds of metres in depth. The La Independencia tunnel intersects the deepest known parts of the system.
- 2) Low-grade, porphyry-type Au-Cu (Ag) deposits hosted in volcanic and intrusive rocks, located to the south of El Zancudo (Leal-Mejía, 2011 and references cited therein).

In high-grade Au-Ag (Zn-Pb-Cu-As-Sb) deposits, various styles of mineralization are recognized according to their shape: veins and replacements in the contact between the basement and the siliciclastic sedimentary rocks, where the mineralization is accompanied by strong silicification and sericitization of the sedimentary rocks; mantles, spreads and replacements in siliciclastic strata, also associated with strong silicification and sericitization; infill veins in N-S trending high angle thrust fault planes; infill veins in low angle fault planes with an E-W direction, which are observed in the deepest part of the mineralized system; and finally, veins and replacement in the contact of Miocene intrusives with Paleozoic metamorphic rocks and Oligocene sedimentary rocks. All these

structures have vertical and lateral continuity for hundreds of metres, and exhibit thicknesses from decimetres to 1 m. (Leal-Mejía, 2011, and references cited there).

In general, the veins are made up of quartz, dolomite or ankerite, arsenopyrite, sphalerite, chalcopyrite, galena, gold and sulfosalts (tetrahedrite, ramdohrite, zoubekite, bournonite, boulangerite, jamensonite, miargyrite, diaphorite) and calcite (Leal-Mejía, 2011).

4.7 GERMANY

Due to the long history of mining in Germany more than 300 sites are known where tetrahedrite or tennantite occurs in mine waste dumps. In several cases, those sites of mine waste dumps are publicly accessible and used by mineral collectors. Hence, sites may be heavily reworked and oxidised. Therefore, the sampling campaign in Germany will take place in at least one out of three provinces where tetrahedrite is reported. These provinces cover different geological settings and include a) the Schwarzwald region, with ongoing mining of fluor spar, barite and subordinately Cu and Ag at Oberwolfach; and b) the Harz Mountains near Bad Grund. Permits for exploration are still pending at any heaps and tailings related to those sites and differ from State to State in Germany. The following generic descriptions will be brief, hence.

4.7.1 Grube Clara mine

Mine: Grube Clara, Fa. Sachtleben Bergbau GmbH & Co. KG

Country: Germany, Wolfach-Kirnbach (Schwarzwald)

Type: Veins (Cu-Ag)

Status: Active mine

4.7.1.1 Historical background of the Grube Clara mine

The Schwarzwald ore district in SW Germany hosts numerous polymetallic hydrothermal veins of various types of mineralization (e.g., Staude et al., 2009; Markl, 2015). Mining of those veins took place discontinuously over several thousand years (Goldenberg & Steuer, 2004). Grube Clara is an underground pit hosted in gneiss and located above the village of Oberwolfach, in the upper Rankach valley, northern part of the Schwarzwald, Germany. Mined for barite since 1850 and fluor spar since 1978 it produced more than three Mtons of barite and more than two Mtons of fluor spar. The mine is operated by the company Sachtleben Bergbau GmbH & Co. KG. It is the only active mine in the mining area and the only fluorite barite mining site besides Grube Niederschlag near Oberwiesenthal, Erzgebirge (Kuhn, 2017). However, first documentary evidence of mining from this site dates back to 1651 and describes the mining of copper ores that lasted until the 18th century. Since 1996, the copper and silver-rich fahlores in the Grube Clara have been enriched by multi-stage flotation with a recyclable content of more than 97%. These concentrates are smelted in Canada and Belgium. The aim of smelting is primarily to separate the valuable silver and copper contained in the ore. The fahlore concentrate contains around 25 % copper and between 1.5 and 3 % silver (Kuhn, 2017).

Grube Clara is well known by mineral collectors and the "Mineralienhalde Grube Clara" is accessible remaining tetrahedrite or and tennantite might be significantly oxidised.

4.7.1.2 Geological setting of the Grube Clara mine

The Schwarzwald (Black Forest Mountains) are part of the Rhenohercynian Zone of the central European Variscan Belt. Remaining outcrops of the orogeny event in Germany are the Rhenish Massif, the Harz Mountains, and the Flechtingen Hills.

Markl et al., 2019, stating “the 50 x 120 km Schwarzwald in SW Germany is a low mountain range consisting of Variscan granites and gneisses which in their eastern parts are overlain by Triassic to Jurassic sediments, mainly Buntsandstein redbeds and Muschelkalk limestones (Geyer & Gwinner, 2011). The basement rocks and the Buntsandstein redbed sandstones host more than 1000 hydrothermal veins, mainly composed of baryte, fluorite, and quartz, and containing Pb, Zn, Cu, Ag, Co, Ni, U, Fe, Mn, and Sb ores”.

Keim et al., 2019, describes the “regional basins were filled by red bed arkoses and conglomerates during the Lower Permian. Due to subsidence from early Triassic to Jurassic, quartzitic sandstones, shales, and limestones were deposited unconformably on the basement rocks. During the Paleogene, rifting of the Upper Rhine Graben was initiated and the graben shoulders were exhumed due to uplift”. The erosion of the sedimentary cover over the last 20–30 Ma resulted in the partial exposure of the basement (Geyer & Gwinner, 2011, and references therein). Erosion was strongest in the southern parts; in the Central and Northern Schwarzwald, the basement cover unconformity is still preserved. In the southern Schwarzwald, the basement gneisses have been eroded to a depth of about 1.5–2 km below the former unconformity (Nitsch & Rupf, 2008). The Clara vein system is part of the Central Schwarzwald and extends from the basement gneisses into the Permian and Triassic red bed cover rocks.

The geological setting of the northern Schwarzwald hydrothermal veins are described by Keim et al., 2018, Keim et al., 2019, and references therein. The local geology at Grube Clara and the complex five-stage mineralisation stating that the veins are hosted by paragneiss and metatextite units predominantly composed of quartz, plagioclase, biotite, orthoclase, and minor hornblende (Keim et al., 2019).

4.7.2 Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine

Mine: Bergwerkswohlfahrt

Country: Germany, Harz Mountains

Type: Veins (Pb-Zn-Ag)

Status: Closed mine

4.7.2.1 Historical background of the Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine

The historic Harz Mountains mining district in central Germany is well known world-wide where hydrothermal veins enriched in base metals were mined between the Middle Ages and 1992 (Sperling, 1978; Bartels, 1992; Liessmann, 2010). The systems of hydrothermal veins often enriched in Pb-Ag have caused mining activities. The eastern part of the *Silbernaaler vein system* was mined from 1822 onwards in the *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* underground mine (Bartels, 1992). In 1923 it was merged with the nearby Hilfe Gottes mine into the underground mine *Erzbergwerk Grund* operated by Preußische Bergwerks- und Hütten-Aktiengesellschaft later known as Preussag AG Metall (Bartels, 1992; Liessmann, 2010). Running until 1992 the *Erzbergwerk Grund* produced about 16 Mt ore of which about 1 Mt are Pb, 700 t are Zn and 2.5 t are Ag (Stedingk & Stoppel,

1993). It was the last producing metal ore mine in the western part of Germany and is now part of the UNESCO World Heritage Site Harz¹.

The tailings of the *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* mine waste dump (Figure 22) were deposited between 1903 and 1931 (Preußische Bergwerks- und Hütten-Aktiengesellschaft, 1903). Situated between the former mining towns of Clausthal-Zellerfeld and Bad Grund the mine waste dump is mainly built up of tailings from gravity separation produced in a stamp mill. The stamp mill belonged to the historic *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* silver and lead mine (Kuhn & Meima, 2019). Water-powered stamp mills were used in the beneficiation processes at many mine sites in the Harz Mountains from 1595 to 1930s followed by beneficiation by froth flotation (Bartels, 1992).

Figure 22: Location of the Harz Mountains in Germany (red dot) and photo of the northwestern part of the *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* mine waste dump (source: BGR). Due to the high heavy metal concentrations of the tailings, they are hardly covered by vegetation. The image width is approximately 150 m.

Between 1903 and 1914 the annual crude ore production was about 25,000–30,000 tons, rising to 40,500 tons by 1916 (Bartels, 1992). Due to the global economic crisis, the ore processing plant of *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* was closed in 1931. From that time on, until ore resources of the *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* mine were exhausted during the 1950s, the mined ore of *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* was transported underground to the *Hilfe Gottes* mine and processed there (Bartels, 1992; Liessmann, 2010).

The mineralogy of the mine waste dump has been investigated by BGR; details to be seen there (Kuhn & Meima, 2019).

4.7.2.2 Geological setting of the *Bergwerkswohlfahrt* mine

The Harz Mountains are part of the Rhenohercynian Zone of the central European Variscan Belt. The Wilson-cyclic basin evolution of the Rhenohercynian Zone during the Paleozoic, culminating in the Variscan orogeny in the Upper Carboniferous (~315 to 305 Ma) (Ahrendt et al., 1983; Franke, 1989; Franke, 1995; Franke et al., 1995; Oncken and Weber, 1995; Oncken et al., 1995).

¹ <https://www.welterbeimharz.de/unterwegs-im-welterbe/motorisierte-touren/welterbe-route-im-harz>

Remaining outcrops of the orogeny event in Germany are the Rhenish Massif, the Harz Mountains, and the Flechtingen Hills.

A flysch-like sedimentary sequence which comprises Devonian (pre-Devonian) to Early Carboniferous siliciclastic rocks, with minor Devonian limestone reefs and altered basaltic rocks (spilite) form the mountain range. In the late stage of the Variscan orogeny (ca. 295 Ma) intrusions of minor mafic rocks (Harzburg gabbro) and more abundant granites to place (e.g., Baumann et al., 1991; Goll et al., 1998). Metamorphism range from very-low-grade (Paleozoic sedimentary rocks, except in the contact aureoles of the granitic plutons, where thermal metamorphism formed hornfels) to amphibolite grade metamorphosed rocks (e.g., Eckergneiss complex, Harzburg gabbro, the Brocken granite) and greenschist grade in the zone of Wippra (Mohr, 1993). Permian rhyolitic to intermediate dikes occur mainly in the Middle and Lower Harz Mountains along NNW-SSE striking fault systems (Franzke & Zerjadtke, 1999). Alles et al, 2019, further describe the Paleozoic basement with SW-NE trending folds and WNW-ESE faults with polymetallic vein mineralization were partly covered by post-orogenic Permian red beds and volcanic and evaporitic rocks. This Permian cover is preserved in the peripheral Ilfeld and Mansfeld–Sangerhausen molasse basins and at the NW margin of the Harz Mountains near Seesen. However, at the SW border of the Harz Mountains, Paleozoic rocks are directly covered by Zechstein carbonates. Together with overlying Mesozoic sediments, these Permian sediments were rapidly eroded from the Harz Mountains during their exhumation in the Late Cretaceous. The main uplift occurred along a wrench-fault system at the north-eastern margin of the mountain range (König & Wrede, 1994).

5 SAMPLING PROTOCOL

5.1 INTRODUCTION

To sample any of the defined types of wastes mentioned in section 4.1, the collected samples should provide representative data of the whole data set and allow to know the spatial distribution of the mining wastes properties. Moreover, the sampling phase should assist the subsequent characterisation (Martínez et al., 2020) and, therefore, the definition of an appropriate sampling protocol is fundamental to achieve these objectives.

A correct sampling protocol is composed by:

- **Sampling method** (scattered, linear, volumetric).
- **Mechanical sampling system.**
- **Sample size.**
- **Sampling mesh.**

5.2 SAMPLING PROTOCOL STEPS

The sampling protocol formulates and describes important parameters for the preparation of a sampling strategy. First, it is necessary to define the objectives of the sampling plan and the objectives of the collected samples. Four steps are considered and described in Figure 23 flowchart, consisting of:

Step 1 - Potential mining wastes inventory,

Step 2 – Field data collection campaign,

Step 3 – Laboratory characterisation of samples,

Step 4 – Data interpretation.

Figure 23: Flowchart of methodology applied to mining waste studies. (*) Sampling can generally be undertaken in two different methods, namely hand picking of samples or mechanically obtained samples (e.g., hydraulic/auger hand drilling).

5.2.1 Step 1 – Potential mining wastes inventory

Includes the integration of historic and bibliographic data. It is an essential step to a good definition of a sampling protocol and field data collection that must include:

- a) Aerial photography analysis of potential areas to be sampled and preliminary area of mining wastes (m²).

- b) Bibliographic collection of any cartographic, geochemistry and mineralogical data and other types of tests.
- c) Organization of geochemical and mineralogical data in Excel spreadsheet format.
- d) Ranking of potential areas for the sampling plan.

5.2.2 Step 2 – Field data collection campaign

Includes mining wastes and material characterisation and mining wastes sampling. For a correct homogenization of the field data, the information form (suggested in Table 5) must be completed according to the specifications described. Due to the high heterogeneity of these materials, for a representativeness of the population to be sampled (mining wastes) it is recommended to collect a **composite sample** composed by a minimum of **4 sub samples** collected randomly. Each sub sample must include an approximately volume of **20 L**.

However, different sampling methods can be used depending on the ore and mining waste type. Spotted and composite samples are ideal. However, the sampler can use other methods like auger and drill core. In these cases, the sample must be described according to the depth collection through a geological log. The first 30 cm of the mining wastes must be ignored. Another sampling alternative could be the use of the UNE-EN 932-1 European standard (Part 1: Methods for sampling). This test was designed for the general properties of aggregates and could be used for stockpiles that may behave like aggregates in conical piles.

Table 5: Field data sheet of mining wastes sampling.

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: day/month/year	
						Country:	
Sample ID: PT/BARR/001/A ¹		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X:		Y:	
Sampler							
Organization							
Mine name							
Deposit type							
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine			
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel	
Simple		Composite		Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh			
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump			
		Tailings		Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Square metres					
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones	
Mineralogy							
Photos		Photos organized by sample ID. Ex: PT/BARR/001/01; PT/BARR/001/02;					
Comments							

¹ - Sample ID – PT – Initials of the country (e.g., PT, ES, AT, DK); BARR – Initials of the mine/deposit/site name (e.g., BARR – Barrigão mine, NC – Neves-Corvo mine, ALJ – Aljustrel mine); 001 – Number of sample (001, 002, etc.); A – subsample (A, B, C)

5.2.3 Step 3 – Laboratory characterisation of samples

The characterisation of samples is carried out according to the scheme shown in Figure 24 below:

Figure 24: Flowchart of laboratory characterisation of the mining wastes. Particle size analysis is optional. **Note** – Particle size analysis is optional, however, it must be considered that the mine wastes material is very heterogeneous and includes different granulometric sizes. For a good characterisation of the mining wastes, for their reuse, it is necessary to have a good characterisation of the different fractions.

Figure 25: Sample collected in the Brancanes mine. *Left* - sample collected directly in mining waste with external patina and oxidised areas. *Right* – Clean and cut sample.

5. Crushing of samples if needed

Invariably tetrahedrite/tennantite may be an accessory mineral phase in a complex mineral paragenesis (Figures 25 and 26). In these cases, adequate crushing must be undertaken to expose the minerals of interest for separation.

Figure 26: Complex mineralogical association of chalcopyrite (yellow) and mixed sphalerite, tetrahedrite, tennantite minerals (grey) in Barrigão mine samples (Iberian Pyrite Belt).

6. Mineral separation and concentrate delivery

Concentration of the tetrahedrite/tennantite minerals must be carried using the most adequate methods given the size, mineralogical complexity, and characterisation.

7. Final XRD verification

Mineral concentrates should be checked for consistency and mineral suitability using XRD techniques.

8. Delivery of concentrate

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